

EXPERIMENTAL AND ANALYTICAL STUDY ON TRANSVERSE CRACKING
AND DELAMINATION OF $[\pm\theta/90_2]_s$ CARBON/EPOXY LAMINATES*

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ABSTRACT

The transverse cracking and delamination damage of the two series (i.e. $[\pm\theta/90_2]_s$ and $[0_n/90_2]_s$) of carbon/epoxy laminates induced by tensile loading were studied experimentally and analysed with finite element method (FEM). In the experiments, the damage process of the multi-layer laminates were monitored with acoustic emission (AE) technique and observed by using scanning electron microscope (SEM). The relationship of mechanical behaviour, initial damage and damage accumulation with lay-up angle θ were analysed. This study indicates that the results measured for transverse cracking and delamination are in good agreement with those of predictions by FEM calculations, in which the energy criterion was used. In addition, compression tests were conducted on the testing stage in the SEM and so the failure processes were dynamically observed. Finally, the microscopic failure mechanisms of the laminates having different θ were discussed.

KEYWORDS: Carbon/Epoxy; AE experiment; FEM analysis; Transverse/cracking; Delamination.

1. INTRODUCTION

The structural components made of advanced composite materials usually are multi-layer laminates. Their damage and fracture behaviour are complicated. In order to lay a solid foundation upon which the design calculations can be performed, the real-time observation and measurement of various modes of failure and damage are necessary, and the investigation of calculation method for predicting the onset of various kinds of failure is also required.

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In the present work, both experiments and computations were carried out to measure and predict the strain (or load) values at which the transverse cracking and delamination failure occurred. The experimental results obtained by using acoustic emission (AE) method and SEM observation were compared and found in good agreement with those of prediction of energy criterion in conjunction with FEM. The influence of variation of θ on the mechanical behaviour and fracture and failure modes of the materials was investigated using two series of symmetric lay-up laminates ($[\pm\theta/90_2]_s$ and $[0_n/90_2]_s$).

2. SPECIMEN AND TEST METHOD

The material system tested was carbon fibre, made in Shanghai, China, reinforced 648 epoxy resin. The laminated panels were fabricated by hot-pressing technology and consist of two categories: (a) $[\pm\theta/90_2]_s$ with θ being 0° , 10° , 25° , 30° , 45° and 60° ; (b) $[0_n/90_2]_s$ with n being equal to 1, 2 and 3 respectively. The volume fraction of carbon fibre V_f is about 60%.

The tensile tests, along with AE detection, were conducted on an INSTRON 1195 testing machine. The AE set-up of SFS-4¹ was employed to monitor the damage and failure process. The number of weight ring-down signal was selected as characterising parameter. The measured results of failure were compared with those of FEM calculations. The dimensions of the tensile specimen are 200mmX15mmX2mm, with the gage length of 100mm.

In order to perform a real-time measurement and observation of micro-structural damage and failure process in situ, some compression tests were conducted in the SEM of HITACHI S-570. The testing fixture was designed and home made by ourselves². The compressive specimen was pre-checked to ensure not to buckle before failure.

3. TENSILE EXPERIMENT AND ACOUSTIC EMISSION DETECTION

Because the lay-up angle of carbon fibre was different, the fibres, matrix and interface in different laminates are subjected to different stresses. Therefore, the stress strain relation of the specimens with different angle θ possesses different features. The σ - ϵ curves for being 0° , 10° and 60° are approximately linear. For $\theta = 0^\circ$ and $\theta = 10^\circ$, owing to the fibres bearing the load, the stress strain curves are linear. For $\theta = 60^\circ$, the interface between the fibres and matrix is mainly subjected to tensile stress, so failure stress σ_{ult} and failure strain ϵ_{ult} are both very small. For $\theta = 25^\circ$, $\theta = 30^\circ$ and $\theta = 45^\circ$, the σ - ϵ curves were seen to deviate from linear at larger load level. This phenomenon is due to the substantial role of the matrix in carrying the load. The turning point from linear to non-linear varies with the contribution of matrix in load-carrying. The experimental results of tensile tests are summarised in Table 1.

Table 1 Tensile properties and comparison of tested and predicted results of fracture on C/E laminates

specimen lay-up	No.	strength	Young's	poission's	maximum	$\epsilon_{ult} \%$	ϵ_{TExp}	ϵ_{TPred}	$\frac{\epsilon_{TPred} - \epsilon_{TExp}}{\epsilon_{TExp}}$	$\epsilon_{ult} \%$	ϵ_{DExp}	ϵ_{DPred}	$\frac{\epsilon_{DPred} - \epsilon_{DExp}}{\epsilon_{DExp}}$	ac. area
		σ (MPa)	modulus E(GPa)	ratio ν	strain ϵ (%)	of AE_i	($\times 10^{-4}$)	($\times 10^{-4}$)	of AE_s	($\times 10^{-4}$)	($\times 10^{-4}$)	($\times 10^{-4}$)	of AE (U_t)	
$[0_3/90_2]_s$	C ₁	574	59.9	0.102	3.84	7								
$[0_2/90_2]_s$	C ₂	547	42.8	0.058	3.15	9.8	27.4	30.2	10%	96	302	218.2	-28%	153
$[0/90_2]_s$	C ₃	317	32.7	0.032	2.21	8.7								
$[\pm 10/90_2]_s$	C ₄	230	42.3	0.118	1.8	18	32.4	30.1	-7%	69	123	78.8	-36%	69
$[\pm 25/90_2]_s$	C ₅	113	37.7	0.179	1.01	29.2	29.5	30.5	3%	51.7	55	46.4	-16%	45
$[\pm 30/90_2]_s$	C ₆	111.5	38.0	0.175	0.8	34	27.2	31.6	16%	52	41	46.2	13%	6.6
$[\pm 45/90_2]_s$	C ₇	53	19.1	0.15	0.94	36.2	34.1	32.8	-4%	62	67	65.1	23%	35
$[\pm 60/90_2]_s$	C ₈	28.4	14	0.12	0.41	73	29.9	37.7	26%	79	33	--	--	31.3

ϵ_{TExp} -- Measured strain at occurrence of transverse cracking; ϵ_{TPred} -- Predicted strain at occurrence of transverse cracking; AE_i -- onset of initial AE; AE_s -- a sudden AE signal; ϵ_{DExp} -- Measured strain at delamination; ϵ_{DPred} -- Predicted strain of delamination; a.c. area of AE (U_t) -- the accumulation area of AE (total energy release).

The tensile strength and the Young's modulus were decreased with increasing θ . Fig. 1 illustrates the relation between the tensile strength and lay-up angle θ . The maximum strain (%) is also decreased while θ increases. But Poisson's ratio ν is increased with θ . The lay-up angle θ has a large influence on the strength. In the present paper, as θ varies from 0° to 10° , the tensile strength σ_{ult} drops from a maximum of 547MPa to 230MPa. For the $[0_n/90_2]_s$ laminates, the tensile strength, the Young's modulus and maximum strain all increased as the number of 0° layer increased.

Fig. 1 Variation of σ_t with θ

The tested results of AE technique combined with observation of SEM indicated that in the tensile tests, when no damage occurred in the laminates no AE signal was observed, until AE signal of small energy release happened, which is associated with the transverse cracking. When delamination took place in the interface between -0° and 90° layers, a sudden AE signal was detected; whose maximum increment ΔE_t and the accumulative AE_t etc have close relation to the variation of θ , as shown in Table 1 and Fig. 2. Generally, as θ increasing, the occurrences of the

Fig. 2 σ_t - ϵ and AE- ϵ curves of $[\pm\theta/90_2]_s$ laminates

transverse cracking and the associated small signal of AE_1 will be later, that is, the transverse crack will happen at larger stress or strain level. The explanation of these phenomena is as follows: When θ is small, the strength of 90 layer is far different from the fibre strength, so transverse cracking happens earlier. When θ is getting larger, the difference of the load bearing capacities of the fibres and the 90° layers is gradually decreased, the onset of transverse crack will be postponed. The interlaminar failure between $-\theta$ layer and 90° layer gives out a sudden AE_s signal together with a larger energy release, (Fig. 2). The variation of delamination strain of $-\theta/90$ interface with θ is more complex, but it manifest itself with some regular pattern. When $\theta < 30^\circ$, as θ is increased, the strain of delamination is decreased. Whereas in the range of $\theta > 30^\circ$, the trend is opposite, namely ϵ_{ult} is increased. The variation is not monotonic. The reason of this phenomenon is that the delamination is caused by debonding and by shear failure, and the shear stress has parabolic distribution. The area under the AE accumulation curve represents the total energy release U_t in the damage failure process of the carbon/epoxy laminates. In most cases, it is decreased as θ is increased. This is agreeable to the pattern of damage energy release rate, but the $[\pm 30/90_2]_s$ laminate gives abnormal result.

4. THE COMPRESSION TESTS IN SEM AND THE MICRO-STRUCTURAL FRACTOGRAPH

The compression tests of $[\pm\theta/90_2]_s$ laminates were carried out under SEM observation. Fig. 3 illustrates the relationship between compressive strength σ_c and angle θ . The curve is concave. When $\theta < 45^\circ$, the load is mainly carried by the fibres; the ultimate stress of the specimen decreased with increasing θ . On the contrary, for $\theta > 45^\circ$, shear failure is dominant, so the magnitude of load supported by the matrix is increased; and the shear stress is distributed as parabolic curve.

Fig. 3 Variation of σ_c with θ

The multi-direction laminates present various failure modes. The main failure modes are different for different θ and are closely related with mechanical properties. During tensile tests of $[0_2/90_2]_s$ specimen, the fibres are major load carriers until failure occurs. The micro-graph of compressive failure of $[0_2/90_2]_s$ laminate is shown in Fig. 4. The transverse cracking occurs first in the 90° layer. When the compressive stress in the matrix reaches its yielding point, the matrix will lose its ability to support the fibres, that leads to compressive fracture of the fibres.

For the laminates of θ being 10° , 25° , 30° , 45° and 60° , the micrographs of failure have similar features with $\theta = 0^\circ$ laminate. From the edge view of the specimen, it can be seen that there are much differences in failure modes between tensile and compressive failures. In the tensile tests, failure happens in the four 90° layers, mainly which are the weakest layers in the laminates, (as shown in Fig. 5). When the laminate is subjected to compression, the effect of variation of θ on the load carrying capacity of the material is far less than that in tension. For instance, when θ changes from 0° to 10° , the compressive strength σ_c is only reduced by 12%, whereas the tensile strength σ_T by 58%. Fig. 6a and Fig. 6b depict that after compression tests, all layers of $[\pm 45/90_2]_s$ laminate exhibit pronounced appearance of failure. The middle part of the laminate is the four 90° layers, which is much thicker than other layers and fails through transverse cracking. The interlaminar separation among other layers is also clear. The micrographs shown above illustrate that the interlaminar as a crack propagation barrier, and the crack growth along interlaminar direction results in delamination³.

Fig. 4 Fractograph of $[0_2/90_2]_s$ laminate in compression

Fig. 5 $[\pm 60/90_2]_s$ laminate in tension

(a)

(b)

Fig. 6 $[\pm 45/90_2]$ laminate in compression (a) failure appearance (b) Crack propagation

The observation of specimen surface (top view) shows that under loading the specimens always fail along $\pm\theta$ direction, and exhibit features of shear failure (Fig. 7 and Fig. 8). Under the action of force, the $\pm\theta$ layers fail along θ direction by separation of shear at the interface or/and in matrix.

Fig. 7 Fracture surface of $[+45/90_2]_s$ specimen in tension

Fig. 8 Fracture surface of $[+30/90_2]_s$ specimen in compression

5. ANALYSES AND CALCULATIONS

The following analysis and prediction are based on Griffith energy criterion of fracture mechanics, that is, the crack propagates when the energy release rate G reaches critical value of the material G_c . For composite laminates, this criterion can be expressed as⁴

$$(\sqrt{C_e} \cdot \epsilon_0 + C_T \cdot \Delta T)^2 t = G_c \quad (1)$$

where ϵ_0 is the far-field strain, ΔT is the difference between service temperature and the reference temperature of zero residual stress, t is thickness of single ply. C_e and C_T are characteristic functions of energy release rate for mechanical loading and temperature loading respectively. C_e and C_T are related to the lay-up construction and cracking modes. For a given material, lay-up construction, loading and cracking modes, they are functions of crack length only. By using 2-D and 3-D FEM analyses combined with double-node technique in simulating cracking process, the energy release rate was calculated step by step, then the C_e -a and C_T -a curves were obtained. Thereafter, the values of C_e and C_T were determined via the effective initial crack length a_0 . For a given cracking mode, including cracking direction and fibre direction on the crack surfaces, G_c is a material constant and can be determined by test. Thus, ϵ_0 can be calculated by using formula (1). Therefore, for specific lay-up construction and cracking mode, the load (or strain) upon crack propagation can be predicted.

5.1 Prediction of onset of transverse cracking (TC) in 90° layers of $[\pm\theta/90_2]_s$ laminates

With ΔT being 120°C and single ply thickness being 0.25mm, Ref. 5 has tested and calculated the same material system resulting in that G_{IC} for 0°-0° cracking is equal to 107 J/m². For the same material system, Ref. 6 indicates that the ratio of G_{IC} for 0°-0° cracking to G_{IC} for 90°-90° cracking is 158 : 228. In the present work, the G_{IC} value for 90°-90° cracking is 154 J/m². By using the FEM analysis mentioned above, the C_e -a and C_T -a curves associated with the TC in 90° layers of $[\pm\theta/90_2]_s$ laminates (θ equals 0°, 10°, 25°, 30°, 45°, 60°) were obtained and shown in Fig. 9(a), (b). The predicted values of load upon onset of TC in 90° layers (represented by far-field strain ϵ_o) of $[\pm\theta/90_2]_s$ laminates can be found in Table 1. The

Fig. 9 Variation of energy release rate C with a for transverse cracking in $[\pm\theta/90_2]_s$ laminates

relative difference between the predicted ϵ_o and experimental value, which is corresponding to the onset of AE for TC, ranges from 3% to 26%. The 26% relative deviation is for $[\pm 60/90_2]_s$ and for others it is no larger than 16%. The results of calculations and tests are in good agreement.

5.2 By similar calculation method (FEM), the $-\theta/90$ delamination in $[\pm\theta/90_2]_s$ laminates was analysed. C_e -a and C_T -a relations in the propagation of $-\theta/90$ edge delamination were calculated and shown in Fig. 10. Assuming that the initial crack length equals to 0.6t, the values of C_e and C_T were determined. The determination of G_c is rather complex. In Ref. 5, G_c values of $+\alpha/-\alpha$ delamination for the range of $\alpha = 0^\circ \sim 30^\circ$ were obtained by combination of tests and analytical calculations. Suppose G_c - α curve for the range of $\alpha = 0^\circ \sim 45^\circ$ (corresponding to $\theta = 90^\circ \sim 0^\circ$ of this paper) can be obtained through a linear extrapolation approach. Provided G_c value remains the same if the angle between the directions of the fibres on the two sides of

Fig. 10 Variation of energy release rate with a for $-\theta/90$ delamination in $[\pm\theta/90_2]_s$ laminates

delamination is identical, then the prediction of strain value for occurrence of delamination can be obtained, (see Table 1). The relative differences between the experimental and computational results for laminates are within the range of 13-36%.

6. DISCUSSIONS AND CONCLUSIONS

- (1) As θ increases from 0° to 60° , the tensile strength, the Young's modulus and ultimate strain of $[\pm\theta/90_2]_s$ laminates will decrease while the compressive strength varies along a descending-ascending line (concave curve). The curves of σ - θ obtained both in tension and in compression are coincident with that estimated by Tsai-Hill criterion.
- (2) It is feasible to use acoustic emission technique in combination with SEM microscopic measurement and observation to detect and monitor damage and failure processes in composite laminates. The results for transverse cracking (TC) obtained by real-time measurement are in good agreement with those of FEM calculations based on energy criterion.
- (3) Comparing the results of TC and delamination of all the six kinds of laminates tested and calculated, the TC occurs before delamination; as θ is ascending, the time difference between the two failure events descends. In the range $\theta < 30^\circ$, the TC onset is far earlier than delamination; whereas the time gap between the two events is shortened for $\theta > 30^\circ$.
- (4) The six kinds of laminates with different lay-up angle θ exhibit variety of features in failure appearances of compression and tension tests. Failure of $[0_2/90_2]_s$ laminate is dominated by fibre fracture. For the other five laminates ($\theta \neq 0^\circ$), the failure modes are all shear fracture along θ direction at the interface and in the matrix. Compression failure modes are crushing failures. At first, TC occurs in 90° layer, once the crack propagation meets the barrier of the interface between two different oriented layers, it causes delamination. This is why delamination happens after TC.

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